

The innovative application of worldbuilding methodology in the education of animation and game disciplines in China¹

Biin Shen

Department of Interactive Media and Games
China Academy of Art
Hangzhou China
biin.shen@network.rca.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

World-building emerges as a transformative paradigm in global design education, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and holistic perspectives. Rooted in disciplines like speculative fiction and game design, it transcends constructing alternate realities to encompass a comprehensive design process. Designers cultivate critical thinking, systemic understanding, and narrative proficiency through immersive exercises. Leading institutions integrate world-building, preparing students for real-world challenges. In the School of Animation and Games at the China Academy of Art, world-building is an experimental approach to facing traditional education challenges. Nevertheless, it evolves to integrate diverse research methods, challenging stereotypes, and attempting to emphasise solutions to real-world problems through virtual worlds.

KEYWORDS

Research Through Design, Design Practice, Animation and Game Education in China

Reference Format:

Biin Shen. 2024. The innovative application of worldbuilding methodology in the education of animation and game disciplines in China. In *Proceedings of the Expanded Animation Conference on Animation and Interactive Art (Expanded '24)*, September 5-7, Linz, Austria. 6 pages.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13133489>

1 Introduction

In navigating the complexities of the 21st century, characterized by rapid technological advancements, traditional design education models centred on specialized skill sets are increasingly viewed as inadequate. World-building represents a paradigm shift, imbuing students with a holistic perspective and highlighting the interdependence of diverse system components. Within the domain of global design education, world-building emerges as a distinctive methodological tool and pedagogical approach, stemming from diverse disciplines

such as speculative fiction, video game design, and filmmaking. Its expansion beyond its original domains underscores its pivotal role in contemporary design thinking and education. World-building transcends the mere construction of alternate realities; it involves a comprehensive design process requiring a multidisciplinary approach.

From intricate societal structures to environmental contexts, this approach enables designers to comprehend and construct complex systems, fostering critical thinking, systemic understanding, narrative proficiency, and proficiency in designing intricate user experiences. World-building cultivates empathy, broadens horizons, and fosters interdisciplinary discourse, facilitating the incorporation of ethics, philosophy, and sociology into design education. Leading academic institutions like the MIT Media Lab, The New School at Parsons and USC are at the forefront of integrating world-building into their curricula, preparing the next generation of creators to address systemic, interconnected real-world challenges. Through immersive world creation exercises, students are encouraged to contemplate the ethical implications and complexities of their design decisions, embracing a research-based, forward-thinking approach to design. Recognition of the role of world-building underscores its potential to rectify inadequacies within China's design education, nurturing multifaceted skill development and fostering adaptive, critical thinking essential for navigating an increasingly interconnected and complex world.

2 Production without Creation: The Dearth of Creative Endeavors in Chinese Animation and Game Industries"

To understand the potential role of world-building in contemporary Chinese animation and game design education, it is essential to delineate the challenges within this educational context. Influenced by the reform and opening-up policies of the 1980s, modern Chinese animation and game design have been heavily influenced by the visual language of Japanese electronic games and animation, struggling to establish their own distinctive styles and narratives. Emerging from this cultural void, the next generation of Chinese

¹ Situated in Hangzhou, the China Academy of Art is currently the sole institution in mainland China to offer worldbuilding course within its school of Animation and Games.

animation and game professionals, particularly game developers, have become dominant players in the industry, capitalizing on the convenience of digital communication and the sustained service-oriented business model. Despite commercial success, the perception of Chinese animation and game development as a result of superficial cultural layers has persisted. Animation and game creation have shifted from being creative endeavours to development processes driven by quantity-buying algorithms and channel promotion strategies, contributing to a mutual exchange and combination within popular mechanisms. Compounded by a conservative political environment, animation and game education in universities in China have long been perceived as relatively lagging behind other disciplines. While some Chinese artists have attempted to explore new territory in animation and game creation over the past 5-10 years, their efforts have been insufficient to challenge the entrenched perceptions of animation and game education.

The Chinese gaming industry has reached a mature stage[1], yet its cultural expression remains nascent. Chinese game developers currently lack the integration of art and science, the craftsmanship characteristic of handcrafting, and the fusion of technology and creativity. This deficit in craftsmanship leads to a focus on production rather than creation, akin to following rules without understanding the underlying principles. Similar to the design industry, the animation and game industry in China is poised for a breakthrough and transformation towards a more creative direction[2]. Moreover, the evolving digital society demands that these industries contribute positively, transcending mere entertainment services. Therefore, rather than solely serving entertainment purposes, there is a pressing need to leverage China's rich cultural heritage and intellectual resources, drawing from the worldwide experiences in design thinking and research. Academically, institutions such as the China Academy of Art (CAA) ² have embarked on reforms from the grassroots level. In 2022, School of Animation and Games³ at CAA launched the first and only world-building course in China, designed to train students in design thinking through the creation of worlds and worldviews and to experimentally integrate traditional animation and game education with design thinking and research. This course represents a breakthrough in design education, embodying Frayling's ⁴ concept[3] of research through design. CAA aims to enhance the research awareness and perspective-shifting design thinking abilities lacking in current animation and game students through design thinking. This paper will explore the innovative aspects of the world-building course, reflecting on the capabilities and challenges facing animation and game creators in the digital technology era.

² Up to the completion of this thesis, animation and game studies are classified as disciplines within the field of ART in China. The Communication University of China is striving to declare these two majors as design disciplines(2024), indicating the need for disciplinary transformation in different historical contexts.

³ The Animation and Game School at the China Academy of Art aims to uphold traditional Chinese culture with a global outlook, fostering artistic innovation and

3 Backscene: The Absence of Issues and Narratives

In the realm of arts and design education, Chinese institutions have long adhered faithfully to the design ethics established by Papanek in his seminal work "Design for the Real World" from the previous century: designing to address real-world problems. However, what happens if the same problems are inaccurate in the current era or within different cultural environments?

In "Design for the Real World," Papanek deliberates on ethical considerations in design prior to the Industrial 3.0 era. While he foresaw the changes brought about by computers in design, he did not anticipate the myriad complexities arising from the interaction between the "real world" and the "virtual world" in the information age. These issues have transcended the knowledge and sensibilities of his generation. Thus, how will contemporary creators of digital animation and games navigate the production of new "narratives" amidst the increasingly complex societal problems and the deluge of information?

3.1 The Absence of Issues and Narratives

'Humankind is facing unprecedented revolutions, all our old stories are crumbling, and no new story has so far emerged to replace them. How can we prepare ourselves and our children for a world of such unprecedented transformations and radical uncertainties..?'⁵

In this context, the gaze upon the world has long been neglected, as it consistently resides within the blind spots of our field of vision. Stanley Cavell reminds us that "perspective no longer represents the distance between myself and the world; it establishes the position of the world with myself as its coordinate, placing the world in front of me, thus causing me to forget that the world is also behind me and I am within the world". According to Husserl's analysis of image consciousness, when we observe any picture or landscape, three objects coexist simultaneously, yet only one is displayed in our viewing experience, while the other two remain as the background of experience, unnoticed. We "see" them without "perceiving" them. World-building, due to its nature of fictional narrative, is often referred to as phantasm, yet this phantasm is not a simple, distorted illusion or misconception, but a structural fictional landscape. It is precisely this fictional landscape that establishes our discourse about the real world. World-building is not essential but instrumental; the question lies in how we utilize the tools of the lower-dimensional world to speculate and infer the essence of the higher-dimensional world, seeking enlightenment through design process. World-building does not purely exist on the side of imagination or merely reflect reality; it exists between the two, at the intersection of perspectives. Through the process of

exploration. It will focus on areas such as humanistic animation and interactive media, among others.

⁴ In 1993, Christopher Frayling of the Royal College of Art in the United Kingdom categorized design research into three types: Research Into Design, Research For Design, and Research Through Design

⁵ See Y.N.Harari, 21 lessons for the 21st century, 2018

construction, and the practical depiction and mapping involved, we are able to obtain a framework of "reality" and perceive the "world". It is only then that the "fictional landscape" gains significance as a "world model", a perspective from which to "view the world".

3.2 The "visualized" world

Geographer Jay Appleton extends Husserl's concepts into the realm of games, proposing that the world can be perceived as a gamescape composed of three elements: Prospect, Refuge, Hazard, akin to a battlefield in a game of point-and-shoot.

Figure 1: Jay Appleton, The experience of landscape, 1975

Professor McDowell of the World Building Media Lab at the University of Southern California employs the literary metaphor of "world-building" [4] to develop a design methodology for constructing worlds, representing a cultural shift in the production process within the film and television industry. This shift reflects how traditionally engaging literary fiction has often stemmed more from imagined worlds than from plot outlines. At times, these fictional worlds bear a striking resemblance to our own, while others are speculative, representing realities far removed from what we know. Nonetheless, most fictional worlds provide us with a lens through which we can view familiar, emphasized, altered, and honest aspects of the real world. Through the lens of world-building, we can perceive landscapes as intricately composed gamescape. Because of this, it is possible to better develop research and design speculation for specific topics.

Figure 2: The World Building Mandala © 2018 Alex McDowell

3.3 World-Building: From Top-Down Structures to Bottom-Up Approaches

Professor McDowell's World Building Mandala delineates the structure of our real world, presenting a top-down system. Following their transition to Parsons New School in the United States, British critical design educators Anthony Dunne and Fiona Raby [5] also adopted the world-building design approach. Their establishment of The Designed Realities Studio ⁶ at the New School serves as an interdisciplinary platform for practising design worlds. Dunne and Raby employ a bottom-up approach, using product design as a medium to expand speculative design tracks exploring future possibilities, shifting towards developing new perspectives and worldviews. This invites audiences to explore and understand the world in new ways. They view world-building as an effective means to open up the imagination, aiming not to design a specific vision for the future but to break entrenched habits and stereotypes, challenge existing frameworks, and reshape ways of thinking from new perspectives. This addresses a crucial aspect lacking in current Chinese animation and game education.

Constructing a "possible" fictional world may not be difficult. However, the greater challenge lies in visualizing this speculative vision through the design process. Unlike Dunne & Raby, who construct worlds by redesigning everyday artefacts, McDowell's creation of a futuristic world inspired by Philip K. Dick's ⁷novella in the 2002 film *Minority Report* ⁸represents a shift in the design process facilitated by the utilization of computational media. In this film, McDowell led the production design team, initially operating as a predominantly analog art department. However, due to the advantages of visualization and dynamic imagery in communication, they quickly evolved into the film industry's first all-digital art department. Many other design departments soon followed suit, signalling broader cultural shifts within the world-building creative process.

⁶ See <https://www.designedrealities.org/>

⁷ Philip K. Dick was a visionary science fiction writer known for his exploration of existential themes, dystopian societies, and the nature of reality. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philip_K._Dick

⁸ "Minority Report" is a futuristic thriller directed by Steven Spielberg, exploring themes of precrime, free will, and the ethics of surveillance in a visually stunning dystopian setting. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minority_Report_\(film\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minority_Report_(film))

4 Design a World' in China Academy of Art

For most people, world-building is primarily associated with working with text. However, the practices of Dunne & Raby and McDowell in product design and film have opened up new possibilities for world-building as a form of research through design. Take, for example, Alex's practice in the Minority Report film. Before the script text, extrapolating and constructing the world [6]through visual and design thinking makes the "world" more concrete and logical, providing artists, designers, and students who use visualization as a creative tool with new avenues for exploration.

However, the world-building approaches of Dunne & Raby and McDowell are still based on Western culture and linear research[7], which contrasts with the scattered thinking prevalent in Eastern culture. Therefore, in the 5-week world-building course at the China Academy of Art, course instructor divides the course into three progressively advancing modules: 1.Liberating Nature; 2.the 24-hour Clock; 3. Building a World, which all aimed at activating students' proactive thinking and research abilities through practical exercises.

Figure 3: World-Building Course Diagram© 2022 Biin Shen

Figure 4: All research processes and data are also required to be presented visually during the course

Liberating Nature typically serves as a module to help students transition smoothly into the research stage, with its content varying annually but all geared towards breaking students' preconceived notions of "reality." In the past, students were tasked with breaking porcelain bowls (an action typically avoided in daily life) and then reflecting on the form of the world while piecing together the shards into bowls again. Similarly, exercises involve replicating real-world environments through rubbings to obtain "fragments of the world."

⁹ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/McKinsey_7S_Framework

Figure 5: The students joyfully engage in reconstructing a bowl

Figure 6: Topography the real world

In the world-building section, the primary framework still follows the basic social structures commonly utilized in the approaches of Dunne & Raby and McDowell (as illustrated in Figure 2). Building upon this foundation, students are not only required to continue narrative development using the 24-hour clock to drive extensive research but also to engage in mutual questioning among group members using "what if/why not" as key prompts. This serves to focus the scope of research and prepare for secondary research and data organization. Additionally, for art students with weaker research skills, the course will provide various analytical and speculative methods from different disciplines, such as the political spectrum and the McKinsey framework ⁹, to assist them in their research process. After this session, each group will receive a bottom-up world sketch. The final part of the course involves each group visualizing or gamifying the world sketch based on their technical capabilities. Finally, each group will present their work during the final session of the course.¹⁰

Figure 7: Two-dimensional diagram of the political spectrum according to Hans Jürgen Eysenck.

¹⁰ A selection of partial student work can be seen here: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1fdFjB83PFkFvDsK4qfHTRcjgEMOOh98m?usp=sharing>

5 Reflections and Experiences

In this section, I will present three examples of students group work in order to discuss some of the experiences accumulated throughout the course.

Figure 8: FUNGUS Energy Fungus, Inc. course exhibition on-site image

Project 1. The project, titled "FUNGUS Energy Fungus, Inc.," immerses participants in a world powered by bioenergy. Within this conceptual framework, students focus their attention on exploring alternative energy sources. Leveraging the unique climatic conditions of the simulated world, students embark on an investigative journey into the viability of fungi as a bioenergy source. Their efforts culminate in the establishment of a fictional energy corporation, presented through a televised commercial animation and speared out on SNS, in which they advocate for fungi as a novel, eco-friendly energy solution for humanity's future needs under specific conditions.

Figure 9: Efficiency First, still image from the game and videos.

Project 2. In the project titled "Efficiency First," students grapple with the future of work, contemplating the implications of a scenario where artificial intelligence assumes full control over all employment opportunities. Amidst this

landscape, questions arise regarding the necessity of human involvement and the potential shifts in societal roles. Armed with these inquiries, students craft an interactive game within the project, inviting participants to engage in a competition with AI for employment opportunities. Through this experiential gameplay, the project prompts reflection on humanity's trajectory within a society prioritising technological dominance, prompting considerations on the direction of human agency.

Figure 10: Interconnected Worlds, still image from VR

Project 3. Titled "Interconnected Worlds," this project centres on a virtual reality (VR) environment themed around Parkour, specifically highlighting the issue of dizziness commonly experienced in VR settings. Recognizing the ongoing challenge of dizziness in modern VR interactions, the project deviates from conventional strategies by repositioning this problem as a central thematic element. Instead of attempting to address or eliminate dizziness, the students utilise it as a fundamental aspect of their creative pursuit, constructing an immersive world that harnesses this phenomenon through a unique experience.

From these examples of student work, it is evident that the World-Building course is one that emphasizes creative thinking and is based on research into the real world. It is noteworthy that third-year undergraduate students at the China Academy of Art had not previously encountered a course focused on creative production: their first year consisted of foundational art courses without a specific major, and their second year involved training in specialized techniques. Thus, the World-Building course represents their first exposure to a creative production course after two years of study. This course not only challenges their proficiency in existing animation and game techniques but also requires them to develop independent thinking skills based on research and information gathering about the real world—an approach that is quite rare in the current art education system in China.

Given the absence of specialized thematic creative courses in the first and second years, the Liberating Nature course plays

a significant role in breaking their previously rigid learning and working experiences. The 24-hour clock teaches students to continuously relate to materials from the real world while expanding their imagination, thus avoiding illogical and unreasonable ideas—a common issue in Asian students' unique divergent thinking style. Finally, the course on world design encourages students to engage in independent thinking about weak signals in society and technology, enabling them to create unique and distinctive works.

6 Conclusion

The experimental educational approach of world-building, as part of the discipline of Digital Animation and Game Studies at the China Academy of Art, is entering its third year. The outcomes produced are non-traditional animations and games, hence still facing many challenges inherited from traditional educational models in animation and game studies. In this process, the course of world-building continues to undergo continuous adjustment and evolution. Through existing practices, the educational component of this course has gradually accumulated into an interdisciplinary platform that integrates various research and design methods. In addition to training in basic disciplinary literacy, the curriculum incorporates research and design methods from various disciplines such as economics, political science, speculative design, and visual storytelling. Students are free to combine different methods in the creative process. Moreover, the coexistence of different disciplinary methods has also impacted the stereotypical perception of animation and game studies as serving entertainment and commercial needs. Through the course of world-building, a future goal has emerged: to address real-world problems through virtual-world solutions.

Reflecting on world-building, it serves as a visual research method through design practice. Given that its process yields transferrable knowledge, the essence of world-building can be categorized under Research Through Design within design education (Frayling, 1993). In his Research Through Design Theory, he focuses on viewing design as a research method, emphasizing the generation of knowledge through design practice. This approach transcends traditional academic research frameworks, emphasizing the importance of the design process itself, as well as the insights and discoveries generated from design practice. Frayling argues that design is not only about problem-solving or creating products but also a method for generating new knowledge. Therefore, the world-building course emphasizes practicality and experimentation, visualizing different perspectives, exploring issues, and generating insights through the process of design practice. This reflects the mission of the world-building course in the School of Animation and Game Studies at the China Academy of Art and within the animation and game disciplines in China.

REFERENCES

- [1] China Game Industry Committee (CGIC), 2023. China Game Industry Report 2023.
- [2] Mengfei, L., 2018, Understanding the Power of Game Literacy, Beijing: Social Sciences Literature Publishing House.
- [3] Frayling, C., 1993. Research in Art and Design. Royal College of Art Research Papers.1(1).
- [4] Cechanowicz et al., 2016. World Building and the Future of Media: A Case Study-Makoko 2036. IEEE Technology and Society Magazine, 35(4), 28–38. <https://doi.org/10.1109/mts.2016.2618678>
- [5] See Anthony Dunne & Fiona Raby, 2013. Speculative everything: design, fiction, and social dreaming. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- [6] Breuleux et al., 2019. The World Building Framework for Immersive Storytelling Projects. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20196400003>
- [7] Mitrovic et al., 2021. Beyond speculative design. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20196400003>